

Research Data Management Policy and Guidelines

An implementation project for the Institutional
Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Wollongong

February 2023

About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

The work that was carried out in this project tested several [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) elements.

Policy element – University of Wollongong (UOW) Research Data Management Policy

UOW's existing Research Data Management Policy and Guidelines had not undergone a comprehensive review since 2017 and significant changes were required to align with the evolving research data management landscape.

Advice on the management of sensitive data was missing from the policy and it also lacked alignment with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Data Principles and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) Principles for Indigenous Data Governance.

Through our participation in the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Policy working group, we have been able to incorporate recommendations from the Policy element into our latest version to ensure that compliance expectations are clear, that researchers understand how to manage their research data in accordance with best practice principles, and that individuals are aware of their broader responsibilities in supporting research data management at UOW. We submitted our draft policy for review by specialists at the ARDC in July 2022 and incorporated their recommendations. Our revised policy has also had input from the following internal committees:

- Research Data Storage and Management (RDSM) Working Group
- Research Information Technology and Systems (RITAS)
- Research Integrity Committee (RIC)
- Research Integrity Advisory Network (RIAN)

These committees have also provided approval for a UOW-wide consultation on the revised policy, due to commence in October.

The Policy now includes information on sensitive data management, aligns with the FAIR and CARE Principles, mandates that a research data management plan must accompany all new projects (a requirement of the provision of storage through ReDBox), and provides a comprehensive explanation of the roles and responsibilities of everyone involved in the creation and management of research data management at UOW. The revised Policy and a detailed summary of all the changes are attached to this report.

Support, Training and Guidance element

UOW's Research Data Management Guidelines provide the operational details that explain how the Research Data Management Policy should be interpreted and applied. Work to align the Guidelines with the changes in the new Policy has commenced. We are planning to present the guidelines in a more interactive and user-friendly format to increase engagement with this information.

Through our participation in the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Sensitive Data working group, we discovered that UOW was lacking a comprehensive data classification standard to assist researchers to identify the sensitivity level of their data. This meant that some research data was assigned with unnecessary levels of protection, while others had inadequate levels of security. The recommendation to establish a shared data classification scheme is welcomed by UOW and we are reviewing the Sensitive Data Classification Matrix (framework Sensitive Data element) to develop our own scheme that aligns closely with the majority of other Australian Universities to simplify the transition to the shared scheme once it is developed.

UOW's Research Data Management training material has been reviewed and areas for improvement have been identified, based on recommendations from the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Support, Training and Guidance element. It was interesting to explore the different resourcing assigned to support and training at the institutions involved in this element, and in order to effectively support for our researchers to comply with our revised policy, improving our training must be endorsed by senior executives as a priority,

with dedicated resourcing assigned (e.g. new roles created, or existing positions modified). This was also highlighted in the framework Culture Change element, which explained the importance of "Generating buy-in from institutional leadership".

Research Data Management Training has been added to our new policy as a specific responsibility for:

- the University (to ensure that adequate training is provided)
- Researchers and HDR Candidates (to undertake relevant training)
- Research Supervisors (to encourage their staff and research students to attend)
- The Research Services Office and Research Integrity Office (to organise research training).

Data Management Planning element

To support the process of planning, creating and publishing research data assets, UOW has recently implemented ReDBox. This tool helps to facilitate the ongoing planning and management of research data throughout its lifecycle.

As recommended by the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Research Data Management Planning element, our new policy mandates that a Research Data Management Plan must accompany all new research projects, and storage requests are only approved once a plan is uploaded into ReDBox.

UOW's Research Training and Development sub-committee have developed a communications strategy, Library Guide, a ReDBox support website and several instructional videos to enable researchers to use ReDBox to its full potential and embed it into existing relevant processes. This support material is now available publicly online and key learnings will be shared with other universities through relevant networks.

Resulting Improvements

As a result of the support provided by the ARDC Institutional Underpinnings program, UOW has progressed much further on its Research Data Management journey than would have been possible otherwise.

A recent survey of Research Data Management at UOW identified that around 45% of staff had not read the existing Research Data Management Policy or Guidelines, and 57% felt that the current training material for UOW's supported storage platforms was insufficient. This feedback highlighted the need to update our policy, guidelines and training material to ensure they are easily accessible, relevant and engaging.

Our Research Data Management Policy has undergone a comprehensive review, incorporating the recommendations from the [framework Policy element](#) of the national data framework. Feedback has been provided by several internal committees and approval has been given for a UOW-wide consultation on the revised policy, to commence in October.

UOW's Research Data Management Guidelines are currently being updated to reflect the changes arising from the new policy. Plans to convert the existing lengthy pdf document into a user-friendly, online resource are underway.

This project has enabled us to develop training material to support our research data management platform, ReDBox. Six short videos were created to provide an introduction to ReDBox and guide researchers through the process of:

- logging in;
- creating a Research Data Management Plan (RDMP);
- requesting storage;

- selecting an appropriate storage option; and
- downloading their RDMP to support ethics applications.

Several ReDBox drop-in sessions were also held throughout 2021 and 2022 to assist researchers with specific questions. These sessions were well attended, attracting over 300 academic staff and research students in total.

Based on user feedback, several ReDBox updates were made to improve its functionality. These included adding new questions to simplify the workflow, and aligning the Ethics section of the Research Data Management Plan with the research data questions in our Human Ethics application form. These changes are reflected in both the Research Data Management Plan PDF export and Human Ethics PDF export that is attached to our Human Ethics applications. We have also worked with the vendor to integrate ReDBox with our ticketing system, Service Now, to streamline support requests and their fulfilment.

2020 ANZSRC codes were also added to ReDBox to enable researchers to assign the new Fields of Research to their projects (previous codes were from 2008). This data will be used in various government submissions (e.g. Excellence in Research for Australia – ERA; the Higher Education Research Data Collection – HERDC and the Engagement and Impact – EI submissions).

Once our Policy and Guidelines have been implemented and widely communicated, we will re-run our Research Data Management survey to obtain tangible results of the improvements achieved by this project. This approach aligns with the “Continual Assessment” recommendations from the [framework Culture Change element](#).

Next Steps

We are working with the ReDBox vendor (QCIF) to improve our reporting capacity from ReDBox to enable us to analyse academic engagement with it in more detail, and achieve greater oversight of the metadata recorded in the system.

We are also investigating opportunities to integrate ReDBox with our other systems such as REDCap (an application for building and managing online surveys and databases) and our new institutional repository to minimise data entry and increase efficiency.

Our Research Data Management Guidelines must be redesigned to improve accessibility and engagement and the content needs to be updated to align with the changes in the policy. Although we originally anticipated that we would be able to provide revised Guidelines as a deliverable of this project, we have received advice from the UOW community that the policy should be approved first. It will be helpful to be able to use recommendations from the Support, Training and Guidance Element of the Institutional Underpinnings project to guide us through this process.

Our Open Access Policy is due for review, and while it highlights the importance of publishing and storing metadata to disseminate research findings, it does not provide any recommendations on publishing or sharing data sets. We will review the Open Research and Data Publication Element to ensure that guidance on the publication of data sets is included in the new policy.

UOW recently took part in the ARDC RISE workshop to evaluate the maturity of our Research Data Management services. Participants agreed upon several opportunities for improvement and one of the key priorities identified was the development of a comprehensive research data management strategy to demonstrate the need for ongoing dedicated resourcing and support.

In addition to the strategy, there were several areas identified for improvement:

- Training – UOW needs to promote existing training material to ensure that our staff know where to access it. Content also needs to be reviewed on a regular basis to incorporate feedback from users, and must be tailored for different audiences (e.g. established researchers vs HDR Students). We will be following the recommendations from the [framework Support, Training and Guidance element](#) to improve our offerings, and monitoring attendance.
- Institutional Repository – UOW's existing repository does not have the capacity to store datasets, which makes it difficult for our researchers to share them with current and potential collaborators. We are currently scoping a replacement system to address this issue, and will explore the option of featuring research datasets in our academic profiles, as recommended by the [framework Culture Change element](#).
- Staffing – Position descriptions need to be reviewed to ensure that research data management responsibilities are specified for relevant support staff. Alternatively, RDM-focused roles could be established to ensure that we continue to not only meet legislative requirements, but also improve in the key areas highlighted in our RISE workshop.
- Sensitive Data – costs associated with the management of sensitive data are currently passed on to researchers. This leads to inconsistencies and introduces unnecessary risks for the university. An overarching research data management strategy will help to demonstrate the need for centralised funding to ensure that researchers are resourced to manage their sensitive data appropriately.
- Data Classification Standards – We are in the process of developing our own data classification scheme that aligns closely with the majority of other Universities, using the matrix created by the Sensitive Data Working Group. This will simplify the transition to the shared scheme once it is developed.

Project Outputs

Our research data management policy has undergone a comprehensive review, incorporating the recommendations from the Policy Element of the national data framework, and feedback from four internal advisory committees. Once it is approved after an extensive consultation, it will be made available on our online policy directory, and other universities are welcome to use it to inform their own policy development.

A ReDBox user guide has also been developed and can be accessed, along with the six short instructional videos. <https://uow.libguides.com/support-researchers/research-data>

The ReDBox support website is available online.

<https://www.uow.edu.au/research-and-innovation/researcher-support/computing-data-analytics-reporting/research-data-management-and-storage/>

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